

Q&A on the Continuous Spectrality and a Related Equation

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ABSTRACT. Une nouvelle question de mon ami Thierry.

This is not an article. It is a private text. But it nevertheless has its public interest (it is simply a behind the scenes piece that refers to a back-and-forth). I take this opportunity to give an advice to mathematicians and physicists, whether young or veteran: reading only and exclusively books on mathematics or physics carries the risk of having a cultural regime that leads to a disease, the atrophy of the brain, and therefore one is no longer able to understand what the culture of mathematics and physics is, losing the sense of history and the sense of proportion of these two disciplines. That is literally what is happening right now, in the totalitarianism of stupid & blind (iper)specialization—We are in full cultural-scientific decadence. (This is a decadence that I will describe in my next book).

And this is why Thierry and I, who are two *discoli* of thought, we are as thick as thieves (*comme cul et chemise*).

CONTENTS

Thierry's Question	2
1. Alors... ..	2
1.1. A Little Preamble: a Brushup	2
1.2. Au Milieu des Choses: a Profitable Pocket-Compendium	3

Thierry's Question

J'ai une question pour toi mais d'ordre pratique si possible: si j'ai une équation type

$$L(f) = \lambda(f), \quad (1)$$

ou lambda est la (les) valeur propre à déterminer et où L est un opérateur différentiel en r (d'un ordre donné). Cela vient de $f(r, t) = f(r) \exp(\lambda(t))$ [or (λ_t)] pour les états stationnaires, au départ on a $L(f) = \frac{df}{dr}$.

Le problème (1) + le nombre de conditions aux limites nécessaires suivant l'ordre de L détermine a priori le problème aux valeurs propres pour les lambda(s).

Question: le spectre en λ peut être discret et/ou continu. Si il est continu: λ peut il être lui aussi une fonction de r et si oui alors comment résoudre (1) dans ce cas là?

— T. LEHNER, via email to me

1. Alors...

1.1. A Little Preamble: a Brushup

I report this section, born from a stimulus present in a previous email; moreover it has some connection with the above question.

(1) As it is known, the spectral theory of linear operators in Hilbert space is founded, as for finite-dimensional spaces, on the definition of the resolvent of an operator. Mais il y a un "mais".

(2 bis) If I call $\sigma(\mathcal{A})$ the spectrum of \mathcal{A} , then the spectrum has three components:

- (i) $\sigma_p(\mathcal{A})$, the *point spectrum*, or *discrete spectrum*,
- (ii) $\sigma_c(\mathcal{A})$, the *continuous spectrum*,
- (iii) $\sigma_r(\mathcal{A})$, the *residual spectrum*

The subscript letters "p", "c", and "r" are obviously arbitrary in this example.

Let us go into detail.

(i) The the punctual or discrete spectrum of \mathcal{A} is the set of complex values $S_{\mathbb{C}}$, for which there exists at least one non-zero vector in the domain of $S_{\mathbb{C}}$ with

$$\mathcal{A}|S_{\mathbb{C}}\rangle = S_{\mathbb{C}}|S_{\mathbb{C}}\rangle. \quad (2)$$

(ii) The continuous spectrum of \mathcal{A} is the one in which we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left\| \left((S_{\mathbb{C}}\mathbb{1} - \mathcal{A}) \chi_n \right) \right\| = 0, \quad (3)$$

where

$$S_{\mathbb{C}} \in \sigma_c(\mathcal{A}),$$

$\chi_n = 1, \dots, \infty$, with $\|\chi_n\| = 1$, is a succession of vectors.

(iii) The residual spectrum of \mathcal{A} is the set of complex values $S_{\mathbb{C}}$, for which there exists at least one vector orthogonal to the codomain

$$\mathbf{R}_{\mathbb{1}S_{\mathbb{C}} - \mathcal{A}},$$

which is *dense* in \mathfrak{H} -space (Hilbert space).

Consequently $\bar{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$ is in the point spectrum of \mathcal{A}^\dagger , where \mathcal{A}^\dagger is conjugate transpose (Hermitian transpose, or adjoint matrix).

(2) Some things to take into account.

(i) The continuous spectrum and residual spectrum are characteristic of \mathfrak{H} -space with infinite dimensions.

(i bis) It is no longer the eigenvalue equation

$$\mathcal{A}\chi = \lambda\chi \quad (4)$$

that determines the spectrum of an operator, but a more refined investigation is needed. Unlike the finite-dimensional case, there is no guarantee that the spectrum is not empty.

(i tris) In fact, there are examples of operators having the entire \mathbb{C} -plane as a resolving set, which admit an extension equipped with a punctual spectrum that invades the whole \mathbb{C} -plane.

1.2. Au Milieu des Choses: a Profitable Pocket-Compendium

We can now skip to the kernel of the problem, Eq. (1).

(1) The solution inherent to your differential operation L is

$$n = x \text{ (we shall assume that the dimension is indeterminate)} \begin{cases} L = \lambda, & (5a) \\ L \in \mathbb{R}^n, f = 0. & (5b) \end{cases}$$

Here is why: $L(f) = \lambda(f)$, therefore

$$fL = f(\lambda), \quad (6)$$

from which

$$\frac{fL}{f} = \frac{f(\lambda)}{f}, \quad (7)$$

so

$$L = \frac{f(\lambda)}{f}, \quad (8)$$

and

$$L = \lambda, \quad (9)$$

once one has divided $\lambda(f)$ by f .

(2) The solution inherent to your function f is

$$n = x \text{ (we shall assume that the dimension is indeterminate)} \begin{cases} f = 0, & (10a) \\ f \in \mathbb{R}^n, L = \lambda. & (10b) \end{cases}$$

Here is why: $L(f) = \lambda(f)$, hence

$$L(f) - \lambda(f) = 0, \quad (11)$$

from which

$$(L - \lambda)f = 0, \quad (12)$$

so

$$f = 0, \quad (13)$$

once one has divided 0 by $L - \lambda$.

(3) The solution inherent to your value λ is given by an inversion of the starting equation:

$$\lambda(f) = Lf, \quad (14)$$

such that, with a process of division, one has:

$$\frac{\lambda(f)}{f} = \frac{Lf}{f}, \quad (15)$$

thereby

$$\lambda = \frac{Lf}{f}, \quad (16)$$

and finally

$$\lambda = L. \quad (17)$$

(4) The differentiation of all terms concerning λ gives the solution for f , i.e.

$$\frac{df}{d\lambda} = \frac{f}{L - \lambda}. \quad (18)$$

(5) The differentiation of all terms concerning f provides the solution for λ , c'est-à-dire

$$\frac{d\lambda}{df} = L/f - \lambda/f. \quad (19)$$

(6) The derivative is combined with this expression:

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda}(\lambda^n) = n(\lambda^{n-1}). \quad (20)$$

NB. When you have the starting point given by $L(f) = \frac{df}{dt}$, the procedure is that of ordinary differential equations. Pour comprendre, la solution dans ce cas a la forme suivante:

$$c_1 + t = \int_1^{f_t} (1/L(\tau)) d\tau. \quad (21)$$